

POLICE AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY IN THE FUNCTION OF INTERNATIONAL SECURITY AND STABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Cultural diplomacy in the security sector represents an important, but often insufficiently researched, aspect of contemporary international relations. It manifests itself through the actions of security institutions, especially the police, in an international and multicultural context, where security is not only a matter of control and force, but also of trust, understanding, and respect for cultural differences.

Through international cooperation, joint training, and participation in peacekeeping and civilian missions, the security sector contributes to the promotion of democratic values, human rights, and a positive image of the state. In this way, cultural diplomacy is affirmed as an effective means of promoting stability, preventing conflicts, and strengthening international security, with security actors positioning themselves as important bearers of diplomatic and cultural influence.

Modern transnational criminal networks represent a complex and dynamic threat to national and international security, characterized by high professionalism, technological sophistication and the ability to adapt to different cultural and social contexts. In this context, the police face challenges that transcend national borders and require an integrated approach, in which cultural diplomacy plays a key role.

Key terms used in the preparation of this scientific research paper are: cultural diplomacy, security sector, police, international cooperation, international security.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the 20th century, security in international relations was mainly analyzed through the prism of military power and relations between states. However, the end of the Cold War, processes of globalization, and the emergence of new security threats led to a significant transformation of the security concept. Today, threats such as transnational organized crime, terrorism, human trafficking, cybercrime, and mass migrations require a response that is simultaneously security-oriented, institutional, and cultural.

Concern for security exists in almost all cultures and in a wide range of social areas, such as politics, health, information technology, ecology, sports, psychology, economics, finance, and architecture. At the same time, it always occupies a central place on the political scene. Security can be most simply defined as a universal human aspiration for safety that is present at all times and in all cultures. This definition has a universal character that stems from the importance of security for the existence of every person, regardless of age, gender, professional, ethnic, national, or racial affiliation. In essence, all people want to live safely

in a peaceful society, in spaces where their full potential can be developed, and in an ecologically healthy environment. This also means that every person, regardless of the cost, strives to avoid all threats and risks that endanger them (Georgievska, 2015:40)

Security is a state in which everyone can exercise their rights and freedoms, which essentially means freely developing their life project (Jakimovski, 2014:67). Unstable and unsafe societies are not only a threat to well-being, but often become an existential threat. Thus, the survival and security of a society are considered among the most precious goods.

The world, which strives towards prosperity, gives priority to peace. Traditionally, peace has been defined as the absence of war. Given that people are at the center of existence, it may be relevant to redefine peace in a human context. Peace prevails only when the situation is conducive to the growth of human well-being. Life is generally considered safe when factors that cause physical harm are absent. However, security exists at a much higher level than mere physical safety (Georgievska, 2015:56).

2. DEFINING SECURITY AND THE ROLE OF THE POLICE

Security is a state in which individuals, the community, and the state are protected from threats that may endanger life, property, freedom and fundamental social values. It is not limited to the absence of danger, but also encompasses a sense of security, stability and trust in institutions. In the contemporary context, security has a broader meaning and includes political, social, economic, and cultural dimensions, with an emphasis on prevention, international cooperation, and respect for human rights.

Cultural diplomacy, on the other hand, is part of a state's foreign policy through which culture, tradition, language, and values are used as means of building a positive image and promoting international relations. It aims to encourage mutual understanding, tolerance and trust between peoples, with culture serving as a bridge for dialogue and cooperation. In this process, cultural diplomacy contributes to reducing conflicts and strengthening peace, especially in multicultural and sensitive security environments.

The role of the police lies at the intersection of security and cultural diplomacy. As a key institution of the security system, the police are responsible for maintaining public order and peace, preventing and detecting crime, and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens. However, under conditions of increased international connectivity, the police increasingly appear as representatives of the state in international contacts, cross-border cooperation, and peacekeeping missions (Gjorgjiev, V., Kotevski, P. 2019:120). Their conduct, respect for cultural differences, and application of democratic standards make the police an important actor in promoting cultural values and building trust, thereby giving them a significant role within cultural diplomacy.

Modern transnational criminal networks represent one of the greatest threats to the security and stability of states. These networks are characterized by a high degree of professionalization, the use of new technologies, and adaptation to different cultural and social environments. The police face challenges that transcend national borders and require international cooperation. Cultural diplomacy, as part of the "soft power" in international relations, enables trust-building, facilitates communication and strengthens partnerships in the fight against organized crime.

Globalization, digitalization, and transnational migration processes have led to significant changes in criminal activities. Contemporary serious and organized crime is complex, transnational, and often embedded in local cultural, economic, and political

contexts. The police are therefore faced with the need for new strategies that combine traditional security measures with elements of cultural diplomacy.

Globalization and technological progress have transformed criminal activities. Organized crime today is transnational, often operating through networks that have merged with local cultural and economic structures. The police, as an institution responsible for public safety, face the need for new strategies that integrate classic security measures with diplomatic and cultural approaches. The link between cultural diplomacy and security becomes particularly important in regions such as the Western Balkans, where ethnic and cultural diversity can influence the effectiveness of police operations and international cooperation (Penninx, R.2000:56).

3. THE POLICE AS A TRANSNATIONAL SECURITY AND DIPLOMATIC ACTOR

Modern police operate within complex networks of cooperation. Information sharing, joint investigation teams, and the harmonisation of standards require not only technical expertise, but also a high level of diplomatic communication. Police officers, especially those involved in international missions, act as “diplomats”, whose behaviour directly influences the perception of the state they represent.

In this new reality, the police take on a central role. They are no longer just an instrument for enforcing the law within the nation-state, but are becoming transnational actors, involved in networks of international cooperation and diplomatic interactions. The police represent a point of intersection between “hard” and “soft” power, and their role is crucial for understanding contemporary security relations between the individual and security.

Modern criminal networks are characterised by transnational action and mobility – members move across multiple countries and use different legal systems to conceal their activities. They usedigital technologies such as cybercrime, financial fraud, abuse of cryptocurrencies and social networks, as well as the infiltration of legal businesses and institutions – money laundering, corruption, political influence, and multi-criminal activities combining drug trafficking, human trafficking, arms trafficking and terrorism. (Jovanovski, 2018:46)

Cultural diplomacy is traditionally associated with art, education, and cultural exchange, but its role in the security sector is increasingly pronounced. In the police context, it manifests itself through: intercultural communication, respect for local customs, transparency and legitimacy, and the protection of human rights. In this way, the police become part of the soft power of the state (Nye, 2004).

Modern criminal networks are characterized by transnational operations, rapid mobility of members, the use of digital technologies and encrypted communications, infiltration of legal businesses and institutions, financial crime, human trafficking, cybercrime, and terrorist activities.

The number of attacks on banking systems, digital platforms, and private data is increasing. The police must develop highly technical capabilities and international partnerships to deal with these threats. Criminal networks adapt to local cultural structures and exploit social and economic weaknesses. Cooperation between the police, NGOs and international institutions is particularly important in this context. The use of international financial centers and offshore zones to conceal illegal income requires the police and financial regulators to act in a coordinated manner at the international level.

4. POLICE AND INTERNATIONAL TRUST BUILDING

For the police, cultural diplomacy is an instrument that reduces the risk of conflict and mistrust in transnational operations. It enables a better understanding of local cultural peculiarities, the building of trust and partnership with police forces and civil communities, and facilitates international cooperation and information exchange. Cultural diplomacy is defined as the use of cultural, educational, and social channels to build trust and positive interstate relations.

In the context of security, it facilitates communication and information exchange between the police and foreign institutions, reduces cultural and ethnic barriers, enables greater cooperation, and builds trust within communities, which is crucial for wiretapping, reporting criminal activities, and successful operations (Schwartz, J. S., Montgomery, J. M., Briones, E 2006: 209). The application of cultural diplomacy can contribute to the improvement of police work through training in intercultural communication, exchange programs for police personnel between countries, and the formation of international teams for joint operations.

The police face several challenges, including differences in legal systems and police practices, language and cultural barriers, political interests that affect security cooperation, and a lack of cultural competence among security personnel. These factors can limit the exchange of information and the coordination of joint operations.

Trust is a central category in international relations. Police cooperation contributes to institutional trust, political stability, and long-term partnerships. Through everyday practical interaction, the police create a “micro-level” of trust that has macro-political consequences.

The connection between the police and cultural diplomacy is reflected in their shared role in representing the state and building trust in international relations. Although the police are primarily associated with maintaining order and security within a country, their actions have a broader meaning, especially in contacts with foreign citizens, international organizations, and participation in cross-border and peacekeeping missions. In such situations, the police are not only a security institution, but also a bearer of the cultural values, norms, and ways of functioning of the society from which they come.

5. POLICE IN AN INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT

International police cooperation is one of the clearest links between the police and cultural diplomacy. When police officers cooperate with colleagues from other countries, they not only exchange professional experiences and good practices, but also become acquainted with different cultures, legal systems, and ways of working. Such cooperation builds mutual trust, which is the basis for stable international relations and one of the key elements of cultural diplomacy.

The police are also often perceived as the “face” of the state, especially in contacts with foreigners, migrants, tourists and representatives of international organizations. The way in which police officers communicate, act, and respect the rights of individuals directly influences the image others form of the state. A professional, transparent and culturally sensitive police force contributes to building a positive democratic and cultural image, which also strengthens the diplomatic position of the state on the international stage (Golubović, 2006:194).

In this context, a significant role is also played by the training of modern police officers, which is increasingly focused on respecting cultural differences, working in

multicultural environments, and protecting human rights. These elements represent a combination of the security functions of the police and the cultural values of society, demonstrating that effective security cannot exist without respect for the culture and dignity of each individual.

Additionally, the participation of the police in peacekeeping and civilian missions abroad expands their role beyond classic security tasks (Wendt, 1999: 98). In such missions, the police contribute to promoting dialogue, stability, and cultural understanding in societies that often face conflicts and division. In this way, they become active actors in the processes of reconciliation and cooperation.

The significance of the connection between the police and cultural diplomacy lies in the fact that it strengthens international security, improves the image of the state, and contributes to peace and cooperation between nations. This connection demonstrates that the police are not only an instrument of internal order, but also an important factor in building stable and positive international relations.

6. FUTURE TRENDS AND CHALLENGES FOR THE POLICE IN INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

It is important to emphasize that in modern societies the role of the police increasingly goes beyond the classic function of law enforcement and is directed towards building partnerships with the community. In multicultural environments, the police are often the first institution with which foreign citizens and minority communities come into contact; therefore, the way they act has a direct impact on feelings of acceptance and respect. Such an approach not only increases internal stability, but also indirectly supports cultural diplomacy, as the state presents itself as open, inclusive, and democratic.

Through joint projects, regional initiatives, and exchange programs, the police also participate in creating networks of trust between states. These contacts contribute to a better understanding of different cultural and social contexts, which facilitates communication and cooperation on sensitive security issues. In this way, cultural diplomacy is not achieved solely through formal diplomatic channels, but also through the everyday professional interaction of police officers with their international partners (Europol, 2023).

Future trends and challenges for police in international cooperation are closely linked to globalisation, technological development and increased interdependence between states. Modern security threats are no longer limited to the borders of a single state, which makes international police cooperation necessary, but also more complex than ever before.

One of the key trends is the increasing digitalisation and use of advanced technologies in police work. Cybercrime, online radicalisation, and the misuse of digital platforms require rapid information exchange and joint investigations between police services from different countries. However, significant challenges arise, such as differences in legal regulations on personal data protection and varying levels of technological development between states, which can hinder cooperation.

Another important trend is the increased attention to human rights and the rule of law within international police cooperation. Police must act efficiently, but at the same time in accordance with international standards and the cultural specificities of the environment in which they operate. This is particularly challenging in joint operations, where different legal systems, professional cultures, and levels of institutional development intersect.

Migration and cross-border movements of people represent another area in which international police cooperation will gain increasing importance. Police will need to strike a

balance between protecting state borders, preventing crime, and respecting the dignity and rights of migrants (Albanese, J. S., 2016:55). This process requires not only security measures, but also a high level of cultural sensitivity and interstate coordination.

In addition, the future of international police cooperation will depend on strengthening trust between states. Political tensions, differing security priorities, and uneven levels of transparency can limit information sharing and joint action. Continued investment in joint training, communication mechanisms, and cooperation platforms will therefore be necessary. These efforts must go beyond formal framework and enable genuine partnership.

In conclusion, future trends present new opportunities, but also serious challenges for police in international cooperation. Successfully addressing them will depend on the ability of the police to adapt, cooperate, and respect universal values, with security, culture, and diplomacy remaining closely interconnected.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates that the police are an essential, yet often under-analyzed, actor in contemporary international relations. Through transnational cooperation and cultural diplomacy, the police contribute to strengthening soft power, stability, and peace. Understanding this connection is crucial for the development of effective and legitimate security policies in the 21st century.

New forms of serious and organized crime require an integrated approach that, in addition to traditional security measures, includes elements of cultural diplomacy. Much more is needed to develop a coherent, strategic, and systematic approach to serious and organized crime and corruption – one that encompasses the pillars of security, development, and human rights, and includes a strong preventive dimension. Efforts must also be made to understand the role of organized crime throughout each phase of the conflict cycle and to design interventions that prevent it from becoming entrenched in symbiotic relationships with corruption and from fueling new cycles of conflict.

For the police, the development of cultural sensitivity, intercultural communication, and trust in international relations is a key condition for the successful fight against transnational crime. Only by combining security and diplomatic instruments can the complex threats posed by modern crime be effectively addressed. Contemporary forms of serious and organized crime require a multidimensional approach in which traditional security measures are complemented by cultural diplomacy to build trust, enable effective international cooperation, and respond to with transnational threats.

Globalization and the increasing dynamics of international relations require greater attention to culture and its potential to enrich and expand foreign policy programs. The use of police capacities through cultural diplomacy contributes to a more comprehensive distribution and accumulation of institutional effectiveness and development.

The application of cultural diplomacy in police activities – particularly in contexts where traditional diplomatic methods are ineffective or inappropriate – broadens the scope of police culture and practice. Cultural diplomacy aims to create a positive image of the country through culture, tradition, and values, and to foster mutual understanding between peoples. This is where its point of contact with the police emerges, as the professional, transparent, and culturally sensitive conduct of police officers directly influences the perception that foreigners form of a country. Communication practices, respect for human

rights, and an understanding of cultural differences are key elements that strengthen trust and enhance a country's international reputation.

Furthermore, international police cooperation and participation in training programs and missions enable the exchange of experiences and cultural influences, thereby deepening cooperation between states not only at the security level, but also at the cultural level. In this way, the police become part of a broader diplomatic effort aimed at stability, peace, and mutual understanding. The connection between the police and cultural diplomacy thus emerges as a subtle yet significant relationship, in which security and culture jointly contribute to improved international relations.

In conclusion, the police are an important –lthough often under-recognized – actor in cultural diplomacy. Through their behavior, values, and modes of cooperation, they contribute to shaping a positive image of the state and advancing international relations, demonstrating that security and culture are not opposing forces, but interconnected and complementary.

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